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Determining the Factors of Turnover Intention of SME Employees in Bangladesh: An Empirical Study

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Abstract

SMEs are the fundamental part of the economic fabric in developing countries, and they play an important role in furthering growth, innovation and prosperity. This sector absorbs a great number to population by creating employment opportunity. The present study examines factors affecting turnover intention of SME employees in greater Comilla and Noakhali, Bangladesh. Specifically the study focused on a survey of marketing executives' attitudes in regards to their intentions to seek out new employment and the effect of the work related factors. Demographic factors, pay and job security had the most significant impact on turnover intention. Working environment, Promotion, colleagues, job in general and organizational commitment did not impact on turnover intention. Finally, this study recommends some strategies on how an organization can retain employees and reduce turnover.

Key words: SME Employee, demographic factors, work related factors, turnover intention, Bangladesh.

Introduction:

Accelerating economic growth and alleviating poverty, generating employment, reducing income inequality and regional disparity are the overarching goals of the current development paradigm in Bangladesh. The main strategy for achieving these goals include creation of productive employment in the manufacturing and organized service sector and withdrawal of labor force out of the low skilled and low return agricultural sector and informal activities. Development of small and medium enterprises (SMEs) is envisaged as a key element in this development strategy. For achieving double digit growth in manufacturing, matching development of SMEs is considered critical. Enhanced micro, small and medium enterprise activities in the rural and backward regions constitute a key component of the strategy for rural development and reduction of poverty and regional disparity (GOB, 2011; Bakht and Basher, 2015).

The Small and Medium Enterprise sector in Bangladesh has consistently registered higher growth rate as compared to other industrial sectors. This sector is noted for its employment potential at low capital cost and the labor intensity is estimated to be higher than the larger enterprises. However, the sector is faced with employee retention challenges, as they are always competing for the best talent employees (Dessler, 2008; Agyeman and Ponniah, 2014). Employee turnover is an important factor for all companies, especially the small and medium enterprises in the course of their operations, since attracting, training, retaining and motivating employees are the critical success determinants for today's organization. Essentially, more organizations are now realizing that is a critical issue and represents a competitive disadvantage (Agyeman and Ponniah, 2014). Employee retention levels depend, in part on the people who are hired, why they are hired, and how they are managed (Dessler, 2008 Kreitner and Kinicki, 2010). A successful SME also depends on its team of committed and productive employees working with it.

The skill of an employee is therefore the key human capital to operate the enterprise efficiently and has to be retained for the development of the organization. Moreover, when skilled employees leave a company, they can take a lot of know-how with them, and thus the company is at risk of losing confidential information to competitors (Furnham et al. 2009; Kreitner and Kinicki, 2010). De Souza (2002); DeNishi and Griffin (2009) reveal that a host of direct and indirect costs arise from the wake of each employee who voluntarily leaves an organization. The turnover of talented employees constitutes the loss of a valued employee and costs such as recruitment, training and general administration are incurred that subsequently hinder SMEs growth and success (Agyeman and Ponniah, 2014). Also, according to DeNishi and Griffin (2009); Kreitner and Kinicki (2010); Milkovich et al. (2010), turnover results can have direct and indirect, tangible and intangible costs and a loss of social capital, which may impact organizational success.

The purpose of this study is to identify the factors that affect the job turnover intention of employees in SMEs. The variables affecting turnover intention are numerous and complex in relation to each other. Nevertheless, among all the possible factors affecting, most studies identified the factors such as demographic variables (age, sex, education, experience and marital status) working environment, job security, salary, promotion, colleague, career development opportunities, recognition and reward, employee communication and job in general (Dessler 2008; DeNishi and Griffin, 2009; Kreitner and Kinicki, 2010; Milkovich et al., 2010; Agyeman and Ponniah, 2014). It is affected by external factors such as politics. Sometimes intrinsic religious belief and personality also influence the turnover behavior. However, the present study has conducted literature survey and found common factors which influence on turnover intention; demographic variables, working environment, job security, pay, promotion, colleague, job in general and organizational commitment. The specific hypotheses are developed on the basis of literature survey.

Relevance of the Study:

There are nearly 1.5 million SMEs in Bangladesh, 60%–65% of which are located outside the metropolitan areas of Dhaka and Chittagong. There is a very high density of SMEs in the industrial economy of Bangladesh. SMEs constitute over 99% of private industrial establishments and provide job opportunities to about 70%–80% of the nonagricultural labor force. The SME share in manufacturing value added to GDP varies at 28%–30%. The services sector is primarily composed of SMEs, which is responsible for the bulk of employment growth. SME contribution to national exports is significant through different industries (WIFIBD, 2016).

Dessler (2008), DeNishi and Griffin (2009) identified, organizational growth depends on practicing sound organizational culture, therefore among all other production elements human resources are one of the influencing agents. The frequent movement of employees from one organization to another, from one job to another or quitting job becomes obstacle to growth. Morrison (2004) conducted study on informal relation in the work place, Ton and Huckman (2008) on major retail chain in US, Singh and Loncar (2010) on nurses, Cao et al. (2013) on manufacturing companies found turnover intention hampers the target of the organization because these employees never think the organization their own, employees can not adjust their mind with the organizational intention. Further, Dessler (2008), DeNishi and Griffin (2009), Cao et al. (2013) found, the employees having turnover intention feel the organization growth is worthless in the context of his/her own interest, employees try to run away from the organization and they do not try to the development of the organization. Most of the studies found on turnover intention are in different organization, no studies are on SME sector especially in Bangladesh, and therefore, due to having study gap, the term to study the level of turnover intention on the basis of some selected work related factors and demographic factor are the vital issues at present.

Literature Review, hypothesis and research model:

Turnover intention reveals the likelihood of leaving the current job by an employee. If turnover rate of skilled professionals is high, the organization might lose the human capital, such as skill, knowledge, and trained human resources to its competitors. Frequent turnover of the individuals incurred both replacement costs and a competitive loss of the company. Thus, turnover intention is a very useful and a familiar topic that has been researched extensively. It is affected by different variables. The literature reviewed by the author is discussed below:

Demographic factors:

The reviews of literature of demographic factor that have been found to have stable relationship with retention and turnover intentions are age, sex, education, experience and marital status. These have influenced employee retention and turnover overtime. Demographic factors have been chosen because they have an influence on employee retention strategies. Several studies in which demographic factors have been employed to investigate job satisfaction and job attitudes have shown that they are strong predictors of turnover intentions (Furnham et al. 2009; Kavanaugh et al. 2006; Ng and Sorensen 2008; Schroder 2008). The most studied and the most consistent in its relationship to quit job is the employee's age. This was revealed in a study by Ahuja et al. (2007) on the IT industry in India. They found that age had a modest but significant effect on turnover intention. In their separate studies on retention of healthcare professionals, they found younger nurses had lower levels of job satisfaction while the older age group of 40 and above had higher levels of job satisfaction (Kavanaugh et al. 2006). A meta-analysis by Borman and Dowling (2008) in their study on teacher attrition and retention, they indicated that those who are 51 years of age or older are nearly 2.5 times more likely to quit teaching than teachers who are 50 or younger.

With respect to years of service, Ng and Sorensen (2008) reported that employees with higher tenure may have familiarity with their work role and have reached a higher level of career attainment than those employees with lower tenure. On the other hand, a further study conducted by Kavanaugh et al. (2006) revealed that nurses with different levels of tenure are not motivated to remain with an organization by the same incentives. Moreover, in a study by Crawley (2005) on the military, he reported that women with five to eight years of service are most likely to leave.

A descriptive statistics reported by Luekens et al. (2004) suggests most clearly that retained employees are more likely to be male than female. In a related study, Agyeman and Ponniah (2014) found males were slightly more likely than females to stay. Aside age and gender, level of education or qualification is found to be positively associated with turnover suggesting that the more educated employees are, the more likely they are to quit.

With marital status, Crawly (2005) in his study found that for single officers without children, 58 percent of men and 53 percent of women said they intended to remain in uniform. This concludes that married employees have higher intention to leave due to family commitment than unmarried employees. Therefore, the study hypothesizes:

Hypothesis 1: Demographic factors will impact on turnover intention of employees.

Working Environment: A well established influential variable identified by the literature is working environment relating to turnover intention of employees (Sharma, 2004, Spector, 2006; Sell and Cleal, 2011). In fact, the findings of empirical studies on the relationship between working environment and turnover intention have confirmed that these two variables have significantly negative relation. Although some researchers in the past had difficulty to find out the relationship between working environment and turnover intention, previous and current studies in organizational behavior identified the clear evidence of working environment on turnover intention. Relevant studies have pointed out that when the working environment is well, employees' attitudes toward work are better, and thus, job satisfaction is higher which reduces turnover intention (Sell and Cleal, 2011). Accordingly, the hypothesis is:

Hypothesis 2: Working Environment will impact on turnover intention of employees.

Job Security: Job security satisfaction as a feeling and evaluation of the employees to the corporate welfare system will have an important impact on employees' attitudes and behavior (Cao, et al. 2013; Cheng, 2013). From the perspective of the development of human resources practice, organizations take actions which are conducive to their secured job. Job securities by the employer have many other consequences; it reduces job related stress and induces belongingness. Human resource management theory has showed the correlation of job security and employee turnover intention was significantly negative (Guthrie, 2011; Batt, 2012). Many of the employees regardless the nationalities worry about the security of their job rather than substantial amount of monthly or yearly salary (Milkovich *et al.*, 2010; Henderson, 2012). Thus the hypothesis is:

Hypothesis 3: Job Security will impact on turnover intention of employee.

Pay: Lawler (1971); Milkovich et al. (2010) and Henderson (2012) suggest that satisfaction or dissatisfaction with pay is influenced by the discrepancy between what employees perceive they should receive for their inputs and what they contribute to the organization. If the input-output ratio is imbalanced, individuals will experience distress caused from guilt of being over paid or the feelings of resentment from being under-paid, and these feelings will serve as a motivational factor leading to restoration of equity (Huseman et al., 1987; Huseman and Hatfield, 1990; Singh and Loncar, 2010; Mussawar and Yaseen, 2013; Akkas and Bodiruzzaman, 2014). Employees who feel under-rewarded will attempt to restore equity by reducing inputs such as increasing absenteeism, insincerity and lack of attention to the job. Finally, when employee fail to maintain equity in pay, wants to leave the organization. Accordingly, the hypothesis is:

Hypothesis 4: The pay of the employee will impact on turnover intention.

Promotion: One of the most common strategies that organizations use to retain and develop human resources is internal promotion (Saporta & Farjoun, 2003; Batt, 2012). The basic argument of most of the organizational scientists is that actual promotion, which is an essential part of the variety of rewards distributed by organizations, affects the quitting behavior of individual employees. A promising variable identified by the literature as an area of further research is promotion influence on turnover intention (Spector, 2006). Early research on turnover intention has also shown that perception of promotion had the most impact on turnover intention. Blum (2004); Spector (2006); Milkovich (2008); Dessler (2008); DeNisi and Griffin (2009) reveal that, regardless of occupational affiliation, past promotions reduced the likelihood of leaving the organization. However, they also showed that professionals (accountants, engineers, lawyers, and computer scientists) were promoted at higher rates than managers and administrators were but had similar quitting rates. Thus, the study hypothesizes:

Hypothesis 5: Promotion of SME Executives will impact on turnover intention.

Colleagues: Help handed colleagues in the organization have been considered valuable for both individuals and organizations. Anderson and Michel (2011) state that friendly colleague increases support and resources that help individuals to accomplish their job, reduce work stress, and provide increased communication, cooperation, and energy. In a several studies conducted by Blum (2004); Spector (2006) also argued that when in a friendship at work, people might feel comfortable with the workplace friendly colleagues and reduce feelings of insecurity and uncertainty. They also share more information and empathies with working colleagues about work-related problems and concerns. Milkovich (2008); Dessler (2008) further stated that employees in a friendship exchange words of

encouragement, confidence, trust, respect, and critical feedback, which may increase enthusiasm and a positive attitude. Therefore, this paper hypothesizes:

Hypothesis 6: Colleagues will impact on turnover intention.

Job in General:

Several studies have shown that people with the same jobs and similar job conditions can vary considerably in their satisfaction or dissatisfaction which turns to turnover intention (Spector, 2006). The study conducted by Sharma (2004); Neal et al. (2005); Sell and Cleal (2011) have shown that dissatisfied employees are more likely than satisfied employees to quit their jobs. Finding such as these have led some researchers to take a personality perspective. Their purpose has been to show that certain types of people are inclined to like or dislike their jobs. Thus, hypothesis seven is tendered.

Hypothesis 7: Job in general will impact on turnover intention.

Organizational Commitment: Many of the authors investigated outcomes of a committed working attitudes and found, among other things, that climates perceived as high in commitment were related to larger proportion of society wellbeing (Milkovich et al., 2010; Kreitner and Kinicki, 2010; Henderson, 2012). Regarding the direct effect of job satisfaction on turnover intention, Milkovich et al. (2010); DeNisi and Griffin (2009) suggested that job satisfaction is the forerunner variable of turnover intention, indicating that job satisfaction has a significantly negative impact on turnover intention i.e. higher job satisfaction leads lower turnover intention and lower job satisfaction leads to higher turnover intention. Although Tett and Meyer (1993) confirmed that job satisfaction has a significant effect on organizational commitment and no direct effect on turnover intention. But many of the behavioral scientists, Henderson (2007); Dessler (2008); DeNisi and Griffin (2009); Milkovich et al. (2010); Kreitner & Kinicki (2010); Cheng (2013); Demirtas and Akdogan (2015) depict the relationship between organizational commitment and turnover intention because lack of organizational commitment causes burnout in employees mind. Job satisfaction/dissatisfaction is regarded as an antecedent variable of organizational commitment. Accordingly, this paper proposes the following hypotheses:

Hypothesis 8: Organizational Commitment will impact on turnover intention.

On the basis of the above discussion, the conceptual framework to be studied in this research is depicted in Figure 1, including the eight hypotheses:

Independent Variables – Dependent variable

Figure 1. Research Model

Objectives: The specific objectives of this study are:

1. To measure the influence of independent variables determined in the research model to dependent variable;
2. To find out the critical factors which influence on job turnover intention;
3. To offer suitable suggestions for policy makers, employers and to make references for organizational behavioral practitioners.

Methodology:

Sample: Using the stratified random sampling technique, a total 284 respondents (top, mid and lower level employees) were selected as samples of the study from greater Comilla and Noakhali region of Bangladesh. The respondents came from various employees engaged in different organizations in order to get better mixture among respondents to increase the generalization of the result. The study period was 15th March to 14th April, 2017.

Measurements: In the study, demographic factors (age, sex, family income, education, experience and marital status) and work related factors such as: working environment, job security, pay, promotion, colleagues, job in general and organizational commitment were considered as independent variables and measure their effects on dependent variable, turnover intention. To assess the result, five-point Likert Scale was used in which [1] indicates “never”, [2] indicates “rarely”, [3] indicates “occasionally”, [4] indicates “usually” and [5] indicates “constantly”.

Validity: To check the validity of the selected variables and their facets, before conducting the final survey, a pilot survey was conducted in the respective areas on respective respondents.

Reliability: The internal reliability of the items used were verified by adapting the Cronbach’s alpha (George and Mallery, 2003). George and Mallery provide the following rules of thumb: $>.9$ – ‘Excellent’, $>.8$ – ‘Good’, $>.7$ – ‘Acceptable’, $>.6$ – ‘Questionable’, $>.5$ – ‘Poor’, and $<.5$ – ‘Unacceptable’. If the Cronbach’s alpha in this study is lower than 0.6, the answering will be treated as inconsistent. The Cronbach alpha of 0.83 was obtained for the instrument. In essence, the instrument is valid and reliable.

Tools of Analysis: Respondent’s profiles were presented in percentages value. For the purpose of in-depth analysis and for drawing conclusion, statistical tools such as: inter-correlation matrix and multiple regression technique were used. The data analyses were done by using SPSS 20 version.

Results and discussion: The table 1 shows, Most of the respondents (26.06%) were between the age group of 25 – 30 years. A 93.66% of the respondents were male. The total working experience between 5 – 10 years was found to be the highest (34.51%). The employees worked at best five years were 40.49%. The study shows that majority of the respondents (40.85%) were holding mid-level position, executive and having college education (66.85%).

Table 1: Respondents' profile (N = 284)

Characteristic	Number	Percentage	Characteristic	Number	Percentage
<i>Age (year):</i>			<i>Tenure at present position (year):</i>		
≤ 25	56	(19.72%)	≤ 5	115	(40.49%)
25 – 30	74	(26.06%)	5 – 10	93	(32.75%)
30 – 35	68	(23.94%)	10 – 15	45	(15.85%)
35 – 40	54	(19.01%)	15 – 20	19	(6.69%)
≥ 40	32	(11.27%)	≥ 20	12	(4.23%)
<i>Sex:</i>			<i>Position:</i>		
Male	266	(93.66%)	Assistant Executive	102	(35.92%)
Female	18	(6.34%)	Executive	116	(40.85%)
Total working experience (year):			Senior Executive	66	(23.24%)
≤ 5	77	(27.11%)	<i>Education:</i>		
5 – 10	98	(34.51%)	High School	74	(26.06%)
10 – 15	66	(23.24%)	College	123	(66.85%)
15 – 20	18	(6.34%)	University	72	(25.35%)
≥ 20	25	(8.80%)	Other	15	(5.28%)

Table 2. Means, standard deviation and Pearson's zero order correlation for all variables.												
		Mean	SD	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
1	Turnover intention	3.739	0.781	1.00								
2	Demographic factors	2.596	0.976	-0.453*	1.00							
3	Working environ	3.925	1.050	-0.181*	0.181	1.00						
4	Job security	2.460	0.827	-0.406*	0.308*	0.212	1.00					
5	Pay	2.620	0.679	-0.614*	0.102	0.365*	0.132	1.00				
6	Promotion	3.147	1.053	-0.242*	0.081	0.289*	0.192*	0.157	1.00			
7	Colleagues	3.460	1.041	-0.189*	0.121	0.084	0.052	0.078	0.286*	1.00		
8	Job in general	3.733	0.919	-0.333*	0.092	0.317*	0.286*	0.174*	0.180*	0.163*	1.00	
9	Organizational com	2.585	0.964	-0.242*	-0.078	0.112	0.163*	0.094	0.151*	0.094	0.166*	1.00

Note. * $P < .05$ (2-tailed), ** $p < .01$ (2-tailed).

Table 2 shows the means, standard deviations and Pearson's zero order correlations for all variables. The results show, demographic factors, working environment, Job security, pay, promotion, colleague, job in general and organizational commitment were significantly correlated with turnover intention. These results support the entire hypothesis (Hypothesis: 1 - 8). But the correlation matrix indicates, there exist significant inter-correlations among the variables. These inter-correlations could impact the significance of the hypothesized relationships. However, the above inter-correlation matrix cannot clearly state whether the correlations shown in the different column were

genuine or false, as these were only zero-order correlations and also because there may be a multicollinearity among the variables. Therefore, these correlations were subjected to multi-variant analysis using multiple regression technique.

The multiple regression test shown in Table 3 indicates that there were three variables namely, ‘demographic factors’, ‘job security’ and ‘pay’ which met all the conditions in the selection of the criteria. Out of three variables, ‘pay’ contributed more towards turnover intention, i.e. for every one unit change in ‘pay’, by keeping all other independent variables constant, it would result in (-) 0.482 unit change in turnover intention. It was followed by ‘demographic factors’ and ‘job security’ and they contributed to the extent of (-) 0.411 and (-) 0.362 unit change respectively in turnover intention for every one unit change in them. The independent variables accounted for 57.1% of the variations in the total variations of the dependent variable. As shown in Table 3, the hypothesized factors such as ‘working environment’, ‘promotion’, ‘colleagues’ ‘job in general’ and ‘organizational commitment’ had no significant influence on the turnover intention.

Table 3. Regression analysis		
	Beta	t
Demographic factors	-0.411**	--6.126
Working Environment	-0.095	-1.152
Job Security	-0.362*	-4.254
Pay	-0.482**	-6.696
Promotion	-0.076	-1.181
Colleagues	-0.107	-2.704
Job in General	-0.123	-2.806
Organizational Commitment	-0.109	-2.150
R Square	0.571	
Adjusted R square	0.473	
N	284	
<i>Dependent Variable: Turnover intention, * P < .05 (2-tailed), ** p < .01 (2-tailed).</i>		

The above analysis indicated that three variables were statistically significant and negative related to the turnover intention, ‘pay’ was the most important factors among the three, it was followed by the ‘demographic factors’ and ‘job security’. Therefore, it is clear that unless the issue on ‘pay’ of the SME employees were met adequately and on the priority basis, any attempt for improvement of other factors may not result in establishing suitable employee structure. However, finally the regression results confirm correlation result’s support for hypothesis 1, 3 and 4.

Conclusions: Employees are the backbone of any organization, they need to be motivated and maintained in an organization at all cost to aid the organization to be globally competitive in terms of providing quality products and services to the society. Therefore, it is important for managers and HRM practitioner to have an understanding of why people would leave the organization and it is equally important to identify those factors that attract people to organizations. The empirical results of this study suggest that pay, demographic factors and job security have significantly negative effects on turnover intention. If concerned authority of SME improves pay structure, ensure job security and fulfill employee needs according to demographics, turnover intention will be effectively reduced. Moreover, working environment, promotion, colleagues, job in general and organizational commitment have no direct effect on turnover intention.

Limitations: To understand the facts about the study in a realistic way and more clearly the quantitative expression of information is represented by data. It was very difficult to collect data from the respective organization on the plea of confidentiality. Moreover, most of the organizations were not maintaining the official records properly. Although SME's are found around the country but only greater Comilla and Noakhali regions are considered for the study. There are many types of employees working in SME sector but this study considered the marketing executives only.

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